

REPRESENTATION OF THE GEOMETRY OF TRIANGLES
THROUGH A RHOMBUS

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Triangle. Types of triangles

A geometric shape formed by consecutively connecting three points that do not lie on a straight line is called a triangle (Fig. 1). Triangle O is the simplest polygon. The three marked points are the vertices of the triangle, and the intersections connecting them are the sides of the triangle. Usually, the symbol Δ is used instead of the word ætriangle B: $\Delta ABCB$. This inscription means a triangle consisting of points A, B, C, and is read as triangle ABCB or triangle ABC. A triangle has three angles: $\angle BAC$, $\angle ABC$, $\angle ACB$, they are called angles of a triangle. (Figure 1). Triangle angles are also defined as $\angle A$, $\angle B$, $\angle C$. The sides and angles of a triangle are called its main elements. The sum of the lengths of the three sides of a triangle is called the perimeter of the triangle. It is usually denoted by the letter P. Also, BAC O is the angle lying between the sides AB and AC of the triangle, AB and AC are the sides adjacent to the angle BAC, and BC is the side opposite the angle BAC.

__if all three sides are equal to each other, it is an equilateral triangle (Fig. 2a); If two of the sides of __ are equal to each other, it is an equilateral triangle (Fig. 2b); __ if it has three different sides, it is an isosceles triangle (Fig. 1);__ is a right-angled triangle if one angle is straight (Fig. 2c);__ acute-angled triangle if all angles are acute (Fig. 2d); __ is an obtuse triangle if one angle is obtuse (Fig. 2e).

Matter. Find the sides of an equilateral triangle whose perimeter is 28 cm and the third side of which is 4 cm longer than the equal sides. Solution: if we designate the equal sides of the triangle ABC as x , the third one will be $x+4$ according to the condition (Fig. 3). Then, according to the condition of the problem, $P = x+x+x+4=3x+4=28$ (cm), $x = 8$ cm. Therefore, $AB = AC = 8$ cm; $BC=12$ cm. Answer: 8 cm; 8 cm; 12 cm.

Rhombus

Rhombus (Ancient Greek: rhómbos, Latin: rhombus "circle") is a rectangle with all sides equal. A rhombus with right angles is called a square. A rhombus (Greek: rhombus - spiral, rotating) is a flat rectangle with equal sides (see picture). Properties of R.: 1) diagonals are mutually perpendicular; 2) R.'s diagonals bisect its angles. The point where the diagonals of R. intersect is its center of symmetry. An inner circle can be drawn to R. The face of R. is equal to half of the product of

its diagonals. The face of R. with one of its angles α is $S = a^2 \sin \alpha$. R. is a square with all angles 90° . [1]

- A rhombus is a parallelogram because its opposite sides are parallel to each other: $AV \parallel CD$, $AD \parallel VS$.
 - The diagonals of a rhombus intersect at right angles ($AC \perp BD$) and are bisected at the point of intersection.
 - The diagonals of a rhombus are the bisectors of its angles ($\angle DCA = \angle BCA$, $\angle ABD = \angle CBD$, etc.)
 - The sum of the squares of the diagonals of a rhombus is equal to the square of its side multiplied by four (for example: $AC^2 + BD^2 = 4 \cdot AD^2$).
- A parallelogram ABCD is a rhombus if:
- all its sides are equal: $AB = BC = CD = AD$
 - its diagonals intersect at right angles

If you divide the rhombus shown in the picture in half, you will get an equilateral triangle.

If you divide the rhombus in the picture into four, you will get a right triangle.

If you turn the rhombus to 45° , you can make it look like the wing of a flying swallow or the wing of a bird.

1. 10-синф учун мактаб дарслик геометрия
2. A.Azimov, B.Haydarov, E.Sarikov Corrected and supplemented by the third publisher-Tashkent; "Yangi yol polygraph services", 2017-160 page
3. This article is the national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan (2000-2005)

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